

Data S7: Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates)
for the three behavioural assays depicted in Figures 1B, 2B, 3B and S17B.

Data S7(i): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=57) of termite workers in response to introduced *Pseudoxylaria* tuft on the comb.

Data S7(i) continued.

Data S7(i): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=57) of termite workers in response to introduced *Pseudoxylaria* tuft on the comb.

Data S7(ii)

Data S7(ii): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=101) of termite workers in response to extensive *Pseudoxylaria* infections.

Data S7(ii) continued.

Data S7(ii) continued.

	Day 0	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
(91)				
(92)		Picture unavailable	Picture unavailable	
(93)		Picture unavailable	Picture unavailable	Picture unavailable
(94)				
(95)				
(96)				

Data S7(ii) continued.

Data S7(ii): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=101) of termite workers in response to extensive *Pseudoxylaria* infections.

Data S7(iii)

Data S7(iii): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=21) of major workers in saving healthy portions of the comb from *Pseudoxylaria* infections.

Data S7(iii) continued.

Data S7(iii) continued.

Data S7(iii): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=21) of termite workers in retrieving healthy portions of the comb from *Pseudoxylaria* infections.

Data S7(iv)

Data S7(iv): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=10) of termite workers in response to two fresh combs attached together.

Data S7(iv): Representation of all data points (photographs of all assay plates, N=10) of termite workers in response to two fresh combs attached together.